

MONETARY POLICY RATE AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: AN APPLICATION OF GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST AND INNOVATIVE ACCOUNTING APPROACH.

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Abstract

This study investigates the causal linkages and dynamic future responses between monetary policy and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria using annual time series dataset spanning from 1984 to 2019. The variables in the model are entrepreneurship development measured as domestic credits to private sector, monetary policy rate, inflation rate, gross domestic products (GDP) and imports of goods and services. The paper applied Granger causality test and impulse response function in modelling the linkages. The result indicated that there is evidence of bidirectional causality between monetary policy and entrepreneurship development, while there are no causal linkages among entrepreneurship development, inflation rate, economic growth and imports of goods and services. On the innovation accounting shocks (impulse response function), the result showed that a unit shock in monetary policy rate and inflation rate is associated with negative shock to entrepreneurship development by 0.069% in the short run and 0.038% in the long run, and 0.153% in short run and 0.111% in the long run, respectively. The result further showed that a unit innovation change in economic growth and imports of goods and services may lead to positive shock on entrepreneurship development by 0.047% in the short run and 0.125% in long run, and 0.006% in short run and 0.033% in long run, respectively. Based on the results, this study recommends for Central Bank to intensify its efforts towards ensuring and sustaining stability in monetary policy rate and inflation rate so as to accelerate the rate of entrepreneurship development in the country.

Keywords: monetary policy rate, entrepreneurship development, granger causality, innovation accounting.

1.0 Introduction

Adequate financing is a necessary condition for the survival of any business enterprise whether small, medium or large. Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) have helped countries in Europe, America and Asia to forge strong competing economies. Countries in Africa in general, and Nigeria in particular, have recognized the importance of this sub-sector and the Nigerian government through various agencies has in recent years developed some policies to support them. Therefore, successive governments in Nigeria having recognized that credit is a critical element in the promotion of enterprise development and growth, initiated programmes, policies and other financial institutional arrangements with a view to enhancing availability of funds for entrepreneurial development in the country. Monetary policy is one of the macroeconomic approaches that government uses to control the economic performance over time. Understanding the nature and direction of causality and innovation shocks between entrepreneurship development and monetary policy rate of every economy is of great importance and is the aim of this study. It is conceptually perceived that increase in the monetary policy rate will lead to rise in-lending rate which is expected to reduce the willingness of entrepreneurs to borrow.

However, previous empirical studies conducted in Nigeria have focused on monetary policy and manufacturing sector or firms' performance (Imoughele & Ismaila, 2014), monetary policy and economic growth (Nwako, Ihemeje & Anumadu, 2016), finance and entrepreneurship (Tomola & Grace, 2016) and monetary policy and growth of small and medium enterprises (Udoh, Gbade & Acha, 2018). Thus, this study will add value to the existing study since there is no empirical evidence linking monetary policy rate and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. In addition, the study of this nature is of great significance to entrepreneurs. This is due to the fact that understanding the link between entrepreneurship and monetary policy rate will guide them in forecasting the future level of their investment. It is on the basis of the above, that this study set to examine the causal linkages and innovative accounting shocks (dynamic future responses) between monetary policy rate and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria from 1984 to 2019. To achieve the objective, this study is divided into five sections including this introduction, section two contains the review of related literature, section three and four deals with methodology and results and discussion while section five comprises conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Monetary policy is one of the macroeconomic approaches that government uses through Central Bank to regulate and control the economic performance over time. It is an economic policy instrument by the central bank to regulate and control the direction and levels of economic activities. Considering the effect of monetary policy on private sector investment (entrepreneurship) Kahn (2010), noted that monetary policy is often set to achieve the objectives such as price stability, promotion of economic growth, realizing full employment, preventing financial crises, stabilizing long-term interest rates and achieving stable and sustained exchange rate.

There are two major control mechanisms of monetary policy used by the Central Bank in any economy at any point in time and these control techniques are popularly known as instruments of monetary policy. The monetary policy instruments can be direct or indirect. The direct instruments are aggregate credit ceilings, deposit ceiling, exchange rate control, restriction on the placement of public deposit, special deposits and stabilization securities, while indirect instruments are interest rate, open market operation (OMO), reserve requirement, liquidity ratio, minimum discount rate and selective credit controls. Monetary policy plays vital roles in the short-run and long-run. In the short-run the policy is used for countercyclical output equilibrium, while in the long run, it is used to realize the macroeconomic objectives of full employment, price stability, inclusive growth and favorable balance of payments (Imoughele, & Ismaila, 2014).

On the other hand, unsustainable monetary policy has negative effect on entrepreneurship development. The process starts when the deposit money banks anticipate credit expansion or increase lending without any rise in real savings. This development may arise from lending of money that was hitherto held in reserve or by increasing demand for more deposits without the need for reserves to leave the bank and that will serve as reliable foundation for the commercial banks to lend more money into circulation. The availability of funds to lend out will tend to reduce the rate of interest rates, which creates the impression that there is more capital available

for investment projects in long-term. From the borrowers' point of view, there is no difference between funds made available through credit expansion and funds made available through real savings. Therefore, the lower interest rate has the same effect as a real decrease in social time preference and that will drive the entrepreneurs to invest more in longer term. At the same time, the reduction in interest rates inclines to decrease the amount of real savings, so that real capitals are becoming less available for long-term investments projects than they were before the credit expansion (Lucas, 2012).

On the other hand, entrepreneurship has significant influence on monetary policy due to its effect on economic growth. However, influence of access to finance has always been a constraint to the development of entrepreneurship operations especially in developing nations like Nigeria. According to Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM, 2017), entrepreneurship play a dominant role in the development of innovation-driven economies such as Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Spain, France, Italy, Netherlands, Sweden, United Kingdom, Norway and Switzerland. It also has significant contribution to efficiency-driven economies such as Latvia, Hungary, Romania, Croatia and Turkey. Naude (2011) and Anokhin and Schulze (2009) added that for these countries, entrepreneurship has contributed more to their economic growth than government activities have done when compared to developing economies. In these countries, policies and programs aimed at entrepreneurship development are reviewed regularly (Olutunla & Obamuyi, 2008).

However, in developing economies like Nigeria, the direction of the economic activities is determined by the government. Thus, government has developed numerous programmes to enhance entrepreneurship and boost economic growth. These programmes are Structural Adjustment Program (SAP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), National Open Apprenticeship Scheme (NOAS) and the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Association of Nigeria (SMEDAN). In addition, entrepreneurship Studies was introduced as mandatory course in schools in Nigeria (Thaddeus, 2012). Despite the introduction of all the foregoing, entrepreneurship contribute less than 50% to gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria (NBS, 2016).

Theoretically, macroeconomic experts have established the theoretical connection between real output and monetary policy measures. According to the Keynesians school of thought, a discretionary change in money supply permanently influences real output by lowering the rate of interest and through the marginal efficiency of capital, stimulate investment and output growth (Athukorala, 1998). In contrast to Keynesian policy prescription, McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) in their hypothesis of finance led growth advocated that market force induced higher interest rate, would enhance more investment by channeling saving to productive investment and stimulate real output growth such as the manufacturing sector.

Thus, the theory that underpins this study is monetary theory developed by Milton Friedman in 1960. According to this theory, money supply which is among the instruments of monetary policy is the chief determinant of current output in the short run and the price level over longer periods. In addition, Monetary policy, uses instruments such as interest rates to adjust the amount of money in the economy. Monetarists believe that the one of the objectives of monetary policy is to achieve sustainable growth including the growth of entrepreneurship.

Empirically, Lucas (2012) investigated the influence of expansionary monetary policy on entrepreneurship quality in America. His finding showed that entrepreneurs are more likely to make mistakes when rate of interest are usually low. He further discovered that during the period of low interest rate, entrepreneurs become foolish. Similarly, Jackson and Madison (2019) analyzed the nexus between monetary policy and entrepreneurship finance in United states from 2000 to 2016. They found that the combination of external finances, internal finances, nominal and real assets used in financing entrepreneurship will lead to determines the effectiveness of monetary policy.

Furthermore, Imoughole and Ismaila (2014) investigated the impact of monetary policy on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria using an annual dataset from 1986 to 2012. The variables in the model are manufacturing sector performance (measured as manufacturing contribution to GDP), external reserve, interest rate, money supply, exchange rate and inflation rate. They applied Johansen cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and revealed that external reserve and exchange rate have significant negative effect on manufacturing performance. Additionally, the study revealed that inflation rate has significant positive influence on manufacturing performance while interest rate and money supply (measures of monetary policy) have no significant influence on manufacturing sector performance. In another development, Nwoko, IHEMEJE and ANAMADU (2016) examined the impact of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria using annual dataset from 1990 to 2011. They used money supply, average price, interest rate, labour force and gross domestic product as the variables in the model. They also applied Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression and the results indicated that monetary policy (measured as interest rate) has significant negative effect on economic growth, while labour force and average price have significant influence on economic growth. The results further revealed that money supply has no significant effect on economic growth.

Kalu (2017) examined the relationship between monetary policy and private sector credit (measured as entrepreneurship development) in Nigeria by applying Johansen cointegration, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and granger causality test. The results indicate the evidence of a long run relationship between monetary policy and credit to private sector. On the other hand, error correction model (ECM) results showed that changes in monetary policy have significant positive influence on private sector credit in the short run. The causality test indicates unidirectional causality running from private sector credit to monetary policy.

Tomola and Grace (2018) examined how finance and entrepreneurship affect economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly dataset from the first quarter of 1997 to the last quarter of 2016. The variables used in the study are real GDP, financial intermediation, entrepreneurship, interest rate and industrial production index. They applied Johansen cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and found that financial intermediation, entrepreneurship and industrial production index have significant positive influence on economic growth. Furthermore, the study revealed that interest rate has significant negative influence on economic growth. Udoh, Gbande and Acha (2018) add value to the existing studies by investigating the influence of monetary policy on the growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria using an annual dataset from 1986 to 2016. In the model, the variables used are SMEs growth (measured

as SMEs contribution to GDP), interest rate as measure of monetary policy, exchange rate and inflation rate. They also employed Johansen cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model as the techniques in their analysis. From the analysis, the study revealed that there is a significant negative relationship between monetary policy and the growth of small and medium enterprises, while exchange rate and inflation rate have no significant effect on SMEs growth. Olowu, Ijeoma and Vanroose (2019) analyzed the effect of macroeconomic policy on entrepreneurship performance in West Africa using a panel dataset from 2000 to 2018. By applying Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, find that monetary policy and fiscal policy are significant determinants of entrepreneurship performance.

From the forgoing, the gaps identified are firstly, none of these studies focus on the nexus between monetary policy and entrepreneurship development. Secondly, Nwoko, Ihemeji and Anamadu (2016) used Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression in the analysis which is inappropriate in analyzing time series dataset. Thus, their result is spurious and cannot be used in policy making. In addition, the study used study period from 1990 to 2011. Thus, the period violates the assumption of Central Limit Theorem (CLT) which stated that for a robust and reliable result, the number of observations (sample size) should greater than or equal to thirty. Finally, from the methodological point of view, none of the previous studies employed Impulse Response Function (IRF) in their estimation. Thus, knowledge of response shocks is very important to policy framework. Therefore, this study applies it to fill in the methodological gap.

3.0 Methodology

This study used annual data from 1984 to 2019. The data was sourced from World Development Indicators (WDI, 2019) and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (CBN, 2019). The reason for selecting this study period is based on the availability of data of all the variables employed in the estimation. These variables are entrepreneurship development measured as domestic credit to private sector (DCP), monetary policy rate (MPR), economic growth measured as annual growth rate of gross domestic products (GDP), inflation rate (INF) and imports of goods and services (IMP). The econometric model of the series is specified as:

$$DCP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_{t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{t-1} + \beta_3 INF_{t-1} + \beta_4 IMP_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Moreover, the study applied Granger Causality test and innovation accounting approach (impulse response functions) in testing the causal linkages and response shocks between monetary policy rate and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. This is justifiable because previous studies employed the use of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression, Johansen cointegration approach, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) in their analysis (see, Imoughele& Ismail, 2014; Nwoko, Ihemeji&Anamadu, 2016; Tomola & Grace, 2016; Udoh, Gbande &Acha, 2018). Thus, none of these studies applied granger causality and impulse response function in their analysis. However, understanding the causal link and response shocks between monetary policy and entrepreneurship development will serve as reliable information for the Central Bank to put into consideration the level of entrepreneurship development when making monetary policy in the future. On the other hand, the knowledge will assist and guide entrepreneurs to take into cognizance the monetary policy rate in making their future investment decisions. The Granger causality model of the variables is specified as:

$$L\Delta DCP_t = \sum_{t=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta LDCP_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta LMPR_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta LINF_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta LIMPR_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots (2)$$

$$\Delta MPR_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta LDCP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta LIMP_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$\Delta LGDP_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta LDCP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta LIMP_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots (4)$$

$$\Delta INF_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta LDCP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta LIMP_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\Delta LIMP_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta LIMP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta LDCP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where μ_t is the error term, $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ are the coefficients of the variables. Causality is determined by

testing the null hypotheses that $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 = 0$ in equation (2) and $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 = 0$ in equation (3) against

the alternative hypotheses $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \neq 0$ in equation (2) and $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \neq 0$ in equation (3). The foregoing is also applied to the remaining equations. Furthermore, prior to the application of Granger causality test and impulse response test, this study checked the behavior of the variables under estimation via the applications of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (P-P) testing methods.

4.0 Results and Discussions

This section begins with the examination of the behavior of the variables used in estimating the relationships. The results of such test are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron)

Variables	Augmented Dickey- Fuller		Phillips-Perron	
	Level	First Diff.	Level	First Diff.
LDCP	-2.710777	-5.033410***	-2.257554	-8.330089***
MPR	-6.860255	-6.207259***	-6.919872	-31.04211***
LGDP	-2.112859	-4.490989***	-2.137066	-4.542988***
INF	-4.022825	-3.883547***	-2.423791	-6.910331***
LIMP	-2.287328	-3.695534**	-1.945365	-17.33456***

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Authors computation from Eviews output.

From the result presented in Table 4.1 ADF test reveals that entrepreneurship development, economic growth and imports were stationary after first difference while monetary policy rate and inflation rate were stationary at level values. On the other hand, the P-P test shows that

entrepreneurship development, economic growth, inflation rate and imports were stationary after first difference while monetary policy rate was stationary at level value. Thus, this study is not interested in testing the evidence of cointegration among the variables rather its objective is to establish the nature and direction of the causality and accounting shocks among the variables. Having known the nature and character of the variables, this study then proceeds to test the evidence of causality among the series and the results of such test are summarized and presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Result of the Granger Causality Test.

Null Hypotheses	Obs.	F-statistics	P-values
MPR does not Granger Cause LDCP	32	19.36390	0.0001
LDCP does not Granger Cause MPR	32	11.55794	0.0031
LGDP does not Granger Cause LDCP	32	2.828891	0.2431
LDCP does not Granger Cause LGDP	32	0.060686	0.9701
INF does not Granger Cause LDCP	32	2.528787	0.2824
LDCP does not Granger Cause INFI	32	0.466148	0.7921
LIMP does not Granger Cause LDCP	32	0.789882	0.6737
LDCP does not Granger Cause LIMP	32	0.992184	0.6089

Source: Authors' computation using Eviews Output

Table 4.2 shows evidence of bidirectional causality running from monetary policy rate to entrepreneurship development and vice versa in Nigeria. This is as a result of the significant probability values of the test. For that the alternative hypotheses which stated that monetary policy cause entrepreneurship development and vice versa were accepted against the null hypotheses. The causal linkages also, means that monetary policy rate led to the development of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship is also connected to monetary policy rate in Nigeria over the study period. It is further explaining that proper monetary policy rate will triggers the improvement and development of innovative activities in the economy. The result also indicates that economic growth, inflation and imports have no causal influence on entrepreneurship development and vice versa. This is due to insignificant probability values of the Granger causality test.

Table 4.3: Innovation Accounting (Impulse Response Functions)

Period	LDCP	MPR	LGDP	INF	LIMP
1	0.191660	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000

2	0.189361	-0.069358	0.012532	-0.160416	0.006871
3	0.253798	-0.108884	0.045670	-0.202829	0.040003
4	0.140652	-0.044230	0.099520	-0.177463	0.038162
5	0.134972	0.001132	0.140830	-0.103388	0.045511
6	0.130339	-0.018932	0.127852	-0.074783	0.033789
7	0.173316	-0.049929	0.092693	-0.083200	0.015621
8	0.170108	-0.056487	0.068452	-0.129700	0.012495
9	0.177037	-0.049197	0.077000	-0.147539	0.025353
10	0.157044	-0.037945	0.097719	-0.135822	0.033453

Source: *Authors' Computation from Eviews Output*

Having established the nature and direction of causality among the variables, this study proceeds to analyze the innovation accounting results (impulse response functions). The accounting technique has the power to present the exact shocks that the independent variables have on the dependent variable and the dependent variable own shocks. Table 4.3 contains the results of innovation accounting (impulse response functions) of entrepreneurship development measured as domestic credit to private sector, monetary policy rate, economic growth measured as gross domestic product, inflation rate and imports of goods and services. The result indicated that the response of entrepreneurship to its own shocks is positive throughout the estimation periods. This explains that investment in entrepreneurship will boost and prosper the development of entrepreneurship activities in both short-run and long-run. The result further evidenced that monetary policy rate and inflation rate have negative shocks to entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in monetary policy rate and inflation in Nigeria might lead to generate negative progress on entrepreneurship development. On the other hand, the result shows that economic growth and import of goods and services are associated with positive shocks to entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. A rise in the rate of economic growth and inflow of goods and services in the economy will trigger the improvement on entrepreneurship in the economy.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

In the estimation the study begins with determination of order of integration among the variables. The study further estimates the causal linkages and shocks among the variables. From the stationary tests the study conclude that the variables have different order of integrations with some at stationary at level values and others are stationary after first difference. On the nature of causality, the study concludes that there is bidirectional causality between monetary policy rate and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria, while no evidence of causality runs from economic growth, inflation and imports to entrepreneurship in Nigeria and vice versa. From the innovation accounting angle (impulse response functions), it is recorded that, monetary policy rate and inflation rate have negative shocks on entrepreneurship development in Nigeria while economic growth and imports have positive shocks on entrepreneurship development. In line with the above results, this study recommended the needs for economic actors or agents to

intensify their efforts towards ensuring and sustaining the stability in monetary policy rate and inflation rate so as to accelerate favorable rate of entrepreneurship development in the country.

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